

Sports & Games-Integrated pedagogy: A Strategy for Combating Mobile Addiction among Children

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ABSTRACT

As we are already in the 21st Century, so we observe lots of challenges in education in our society. But Mobile addiction among children has emerged as a significant challenge for parents, teachers, and educators. In 21st century not only challenges are there but also lots of opportunities are available like online learning portals, Technology integrated-pedagogy, blended learning, Flipped class room etc. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasizes sports, games, and physical activity-integrated pedagogy. So, we can look it as a key opportunity to combat mobile addiction and promote holistic learning. The main aim of the present Study is to Explore Sports and Games Integrated Pedagogy as a strategic approach to mitigate the Mobile addiction among children. By the conceptual analysing the impact of Mobile addiction and Sports and Games Integrated pedagogical models on Children's behavioural patterns, academic performance, and well-being, the Study will find a sustainable solution to combat Mobile Addiction among Children. The Study will serve as a catalyst for reimagining the future of education, health and welling of children, fostering interdisciplinary collaborations, and developing actionable strategies to make education more inclusive, future-ready, and impactful in shaping a knowledge-driven and healthy society.

Keywords: Sports & Game integrated Pedagogy, Mobile Addiction, Strategy, Children

Introduction:

As we are already in the 21st Century, so we observe lots of challenges in education in our society like as digital divide, limited access to technology, high costs, and a lack of qualified teachers, But Mobile addiction among children has emerged as a significant challenge for parents, teachers, and educators. Specially the from Covid-19 pandemic accessibility of mobile among children are increased. Parents give mobile phone to their children for Learning but children enjoying in short videos, mobile games etc. along with learning and even some children badly addicted to mobile phone. Excessive screen time on mobile for watching videos, playing PUBG, Free Fire and other mobile games leads to reduced physical activity, divert from real Academic Educational Goals, poor concentration, it also leads to emotional imbalances, poor social interactions. And we know that children are future pillars of our nation. So, making it imperative

to find sustainable solutions. In 21st century not only challenges are there but also lots of opportunities are available like online learning portals, Technology integrated-pedagogy, blended learning, Flipped class room etc. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasizes sports, games, and physical activity-integrated pedagogy. So, we can look it as a key opportunity to combat mobile addiction and promote holistic learning.

Now a days mobile phones are a boon to the student for learning. But every coin has two sides hence similar to most of the Scientific invention mobile also has many attributes and characteristics that make it very attractive to children, young and old. Because of the attractiveness children get caught up in the attractive features of mobile phone and in this way they dependent on mobile phone, this dependency is termed as Mobile addiction. Behavioural addiction for mobile

phones has been variously termed as mobile phone dependence or addiction or problematic use which make a person unable to regulate its use leading to negative consequences in daily life. It has emerged as a challenging public health issue, it also leads to social, behavioural and affective problems.

Sports and Games both are activities involve some set of rules but both terms are different. Sports often involve physical activities and is often competitive and organized. Sports use, maintain, or improved high degree of physical efforts, stamina, athleticism, ability and skills. Sport is usually governed by a set of rules or customs, which serve to ensure fair competition. Winning can be determined by physical events and depends on individual skill and physical strength such as scoring goals or crossing a line first. A game is a structured type of play, usually undertaken for entertainment and fun, and sometimes used as an educational tool. Many games are also considered to be work (such as professional players of spectator sports or games) or art (such as jigsaw puzzles or games involving an artistic layout such as card game/Tash, or some video games). Games generally involve mental or physical stimulation, and often both. Many games help develop practical skills, serve as a form of exercise, or otherwise perform an educational, simulational, or psychological role. In Games winning is depends on the collective responsibility of team, depending on the cohesion within the team. We can say that all sports are Games but not all Games are Sports. But according to some organisations, such as the council of Europe, the International Olympic Committee and Sport Accord, the international sports federation association some competitive, but non-physical sports like chess, bridge (card game), draughts & Go (bord game), and xiangqi (chines bord game) etc. are classified as sports.

Strategy is a plan of action designed to achieve a long-term goal, so combating the mobile addiction among children is our goal and by integrating Sports, Games and Physical activities in the traditional pedagogy, we can mitigate the mobile addiction among children.

Research questions:

The following research questions have prompted the researchers to carry out the study:

- i. What are the Sports and Games integrated

pedagogy?

- ii. What are the Impacts of Sports and Games integrated pedagogy?
- iii. What is the mobile addiction among children?
- iv. What are the strategies to combat mobile addiction among children?

Research Methodology:

The research methodology of this paper is qualitative approach, literature review technique and observation of behaviours, and cultural phenomena with respect to Sports & Games integrated pedagogy and a Strategy for Combating Mobile Addiction among Children. The secondary data sources used for this study are online research journals, newspaper articles, all these were used for obtaining a diverse and rich variety of information.

Review related Literature

Concept of Sorts and Games Integrated Pedagogy

“Sports-integration is another cross-curricular pedagogical approach that utilizes physical activities including indigenous sports, in pedagogical practices to help in developing skills such as collaboration, self-initiative, self-direction, self-discipline, teamwork, responsibility, citizenship, etc. Sports-integrated learning will be undertaken in classroom transactions to help students adopt fitness as a lifelong attitude and to achieve the related life skills along with the levels of fitness as envisaged in the Fit India Movement. The need to integrate sports in education is well recognized as it serves to foster holistic development by promoting physical and psychological well-being while also enhancing cognitive abilities” (NEP-2020). Game-Integrated pedagogy is approach of learning processes inherent in behaviourism theories, cognitivism, constructivism, and such type of other theory (Ertmer & Newby, 2013; Kim, Roh, & Cho, 2016; Li & Tsai, 2013). Sports pedagogy is not a universal defined term. Because there is no international agreement on the preferred terms (sport pedagogy or physical education pedagogy). It is locally or nationally defined in all matters relating to pedagogy and human movement .

Impacts of Sports and Games Integrated Pedagogy

The impact of sport and its socially significant role is also crucial for combating the various forms of

aggression and depression (Petrova et al. 2020). Sport is a complex process that enhance the physical, psychological and personality of children and adolescents, and is very important factor for maintaining, preserving and improving health and wellbeing (Petrova et al., 2022). In most European countries, the aim of teaching methodology is the meaning making and encouraging the desire of each student to engage in regular physical activity, which is important not only for maintaining the fitness of body but also important for healthy cognition (Merdzhanova, et al., 2021).

By using sport-integrated pedagogy a teacher can promote optimal learning among students. Education through the pedagogical technique students connect subject matter with indigenous and their native sports and games that helps to easily understand the complex concept. If teacher use the pedagogy than develop a variety of competencies and skills such as planning, problem-solving, decision-making, logical thinking, reflective thinking, emotional intelligence, feeling of cooperation, team spirit. And develop the capabilities to cope with mistake, competition, deferring gratification among children (Padhan, M & Srivastava, S., 2024).

Game-based learning improves achievement, increases motivation, develops positive attitude towards mathematics, develops the capabilities of daily life mathematics and computation, develops the achievement in recognizing mathematical signs and symbols (Martin, L., 2018). Physical activities and sports develop positive social behaviour, develop leadership skills, social and emotional intelligence among students and hence connect students to school and society (Stead, R & Nevill, M., 2010). Sports is a process that improves physical, mental and psychological health, improves concentration and quality of sleep, and reduce anxiety, depression and other psychological disorder (Becheva, V., et al., 2023). Various folk games and traditional sports provide great effect such that develops social cognition, build relationship with the surrounding environment, reduce inferiority and develop superiority towards their culture and community (Julianti, R.R., et al., 2024).

After studying the above research papers, we can conclude that Impacts of Sports and Games

Integrated pedagogy is very positive, through the pedagogical technique promote optimal learning, improves social connectedness, increases students' engagement in teaching learning process, develops positive attitude towards school and learning, increases confidence level, improves physical, cognitive and psychomotor development, develops social and self-intelligence etc. It helps to develop a variety of competencies and skills related to planning, problem-solving, decision-making, logical thinking, reflective thinking, critical thinking, and creativity. Sports and Games-Integrated pedagogy Improves social intelligence, emotional intelligence, ability to deal with mistakes, deferring gratification, cooperation, and competition in students. It also helps to reduce inferiority towards their native culture. And hence we can say that through the pedagogical technique all round and holistic development are possible.

Mobile addiction among children:

Children who belong to above poverty line and higher education of father were at risk of developing mobile phone addiction. And its negative effects were explored by the study such as Vision Problem, Psychological distress and power of concentration (Sulaiman, R et al., 2021).

WHO has defined online game addiction or game disorder in the 11th revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) as a gaming behaviour, digital gaming or video gaming. Internet gaming disorder is gaming addiction which leads to pathological gambling and severe mental issues (WHO-ICD-11, 2020). Online game addiction is very problematic for children and adolescents. The study has shown that the obsession with spending too much time playing mobile games is dangerous like alcohol or drug abuse. Addiction to online games also causes of other mental disorders, such as stress, depression, and anxiety disorders. (Guerada, K., 2021).

Regardless of the socioeconomic status the accessibility and the owning of the mobile phones is same across the socioeconomic status. It has a negative impact on physical and psychosocial health of children. (Reddy, D. P., & Earan, S. K., 2023). Digital game playing among children may cause of various mental health problems such as anxiety, depression aggressive attitudes and physical problem such as musculoskeletal disease, eye problems and

sleeping problem (Mustafa, R & Yasaci, Z., 2018).

An observation of researcher in his village is that some children who received laissez-faire parenting, they used to mobile as per their wish. Gradually the children became addicted to mobile games, decreased social interaction, became academically very weak. Now when the parents try to force for removing bad habit, they threaten to commit suicide. Hence, we conclude that mobile addiction among children is very dangerous it ruins not only the lives of the children but also the entire family.

A strategy for combating mobile addiction among children

Physical activity and sports, help others sincerely, maintain positive thoughts reduce mobile addiction among children. Developing the ability to solve problems, take counsellor's help if needed, maintain good relationships with others, maintain adequate sleep and rest are all ways to reduce online gaming addiction in children (Guerada, K., 2021). To stop mobile addiction among children, encourage alternative activities such as sports activities or spending time with family and friends. Encouraging and motivating the children to find other interests or hobbies outside the screen and stick with them. Planning family Indoor and outdoor game. Demonstrating to children that these are very satisfying and interesting ways to pass the time than staring at screens! These are great ways to combat mobile addiction among children (Nalanda international school). The exercise intervention significantly reduced mobile phone addiction in adolescents (Li, Z et al., 2023). Educate about sustainable and accessible use of internet, providing appropriate parenting strategies, suggesting alternative activities and appropriate guiding and counselling combat the mobile addiction among children.

Result and Discussion :

1st research question is that what are the Sports and Games integrated pedagogy?

Answer: Sports and Games integrated pedagogy are technique of teaching-learning process by which a teacher integrates the appropriate sports, physical activity and games with traditional teaching method corresponding to characteristics of subject matter and learner. It is teaching module that is prepared keeping in mind the culture and individual

differences of learners.

2nd research question is that what are the Impacts of Sports and Games integrated pedagogy?

Answer: In the light of above literatures reviews it is clear that the Impacts of Sports and Games integrated pedagogy are positive. Through the pedagogical technique promote optimal learning, improves social connectedness, increases students' engagement in teaching learning process, develops positive attitude towards school and learning, increases confidence level, improves physical, cognitive and psychomotor development, etc. It helps to develop a variety of competencies and skills related to planning, problem-solving, decision-making, logical thinking, reflective thinking, critical thinking, and creativity. Sports and Games-Integrated pedagogy Improves social and self-intelligence, emotional intelligence, ability to deal with mistakes, deferring gratification, cooperation, and competition in students. It also helps to reduce inferiority towards their native culture.

3rd research question is that what is the mobile addiction among children?

Answer: In the light of above literature reviews we can define the mobile addiction among children. It is a problematic condition in which children excessive and compulsive use of smartphones, tablets, or other digital devices. They are restless without phone, and when in the class don't concentrate on his studies. Some signs of mobile addicted children such as poor concentration, poor quality of sleeping, and aggressive behaviour etc. It may cause of various mental health problems such as anxiety, depression, aggressive attitudes and physical problem such as musculoskeletal disease, eye problems and sleeping problem.

4th research question is that what are the strategies to combat mobile addiction among children?

Answer: By literature reviews we found out some strategies to combat mobile addiction among children such as physical activity, sports and games-integrated pedagogy combat mobile addiction among children because Sports and Games-integrated pedagogy increases students' engagement in teaching learning process. And if students' engagement in the teaching learning process will be increase then it leads

to concentrate mind and it is sign of reducing mobile addiction among children. Gradually commitment of addicted children will be changed and developing positive attitude towards learning. Other strategy also found out such as educate about sustainable and accessible use of internet, providing appropriate parenting strategies, planning family game, suggesting alternative activities and appropriate guiding and counselling. Demonstrating to children that these are very satisfying and interesting ways to pass the time than staring at screens! These are great ways to combat mobile addiction among children.

Conclusion:

Mobile addiction among children is one of significant challenge of 21st century for parents, teachers, and educators. Which can be Combat by using Sports and Games-Integrated pedagogy in the class room and by appropriate parenting strategies. Hence teacher, educator and parents together can combat mobile addiction.

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